

MuSTAT: Face Ageing using Multi-Scale Target Age Style Transfer

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Abstract. Most existing bottleneck-based Generative Adversarial Networks suffer from ghosting artifacts or blur for generating ageing results with an increased age gap. Although this can be solved using data collected over long age spans, it is challenging and tedious. This work proposes a multi-scale target age-based style face ageing model using an encoder-decoder architecture to generate high-fidelity face images under ageing. Further, we propose using skip connections with selective transfer units (STU) in the encoder-decoder architecture to adaptively select and modify the encoder feature to enhance face ageing results. Unlike conditional GAN (cGAN) approaches that rely on age as a condition to train the generator, we used style information gathered from a random image of the target age group to train the generator. The qualitative and quantitative results on public datasets show that our model can generate photo-realistic synthetic face images of the target age group. The proposed model can also generate diverse age groups for age progression and regression tasks. Furthermore, the analysis using six different Face Recognition Systems (FRS) also indicates the ability of the proposed approach to preserve the identity resulting in 89.82% False Non Match Rate (FNMR) at False Match Rate (FMR) of 0.0001%.

Keywords: Face ageing · Face recognition · Style transfer · Age estimation.

1 Introduction

Face age progression finds its application in wide domains, such as finding missing children, digital entertainment, post-cosmetic surgery, and cross-age face recognition, to name a few. Conventional approaches for face ageing are technically classified into two categories such as prototype model and physical model. The former approach aims to simulate ageing on a given image using images for different ages and the mean face across ages [15, 25] to derive a prototype and extract a texture difference between the prototypes. The latter synthesizes realistic age-progressed images by considering the anatomy, facial muscles, and wrinkles of skin [31].

However, these approaches generally require longitudinal face sequences of the same subject with a broad range of ages and this type of data collection is arduous and

Fig. 1: Fig (a) Illustration of ageing uniformity by GAN-driven ageing approaches as compared to MuSTAT and Fig (b) Illustration of ageing pattern effect by MuSTAT .

expensive to collect in practice. To handle this issue, several deep learning-based GAN-driven face ageing approaches have been developed [36, 33, 32]. These approaches usually employ (i) manifold learning, and (ii) feature translation with source image and target attribute vector as input.

Despite their extensive deployment, manifold networks [36, 3] remain insufficient for preserving identity. To optimize face ageing while preserving identity, researchers have used feature-translation-based methods [33, 32]. However, the feature translation networks fail in generating face-age progression with high fidelity due to altered on ageing related pattern. Therefore, many researchers have suggested adding skip connections between the encoder and decoder layers of the base generator in GAN as a remedy [19]. Despite improving the quality of facial age progression, skip connections harm the attribute manipulation abilities of the feature translation models. Another possible solution is to employ an attention block to allow for attribute-specific region modification. However, such an approach is effective only for local face regions and is not designed for global attribute manipulation [23, 35] (e.g., beard, wrinkle on adult and old-age groups). In particular, the encoders in earlier works [36, 3] utilized only the source image as input to produce a latent vector and concatenate the age attribute with this vector. The decoder utilizes both latent and age vectors to generate age-progressive faces. In contrast, feature translation requires input from the source image and target age vector. Selecting the target age group to be modified while editing an individual’s face age is important. Taking the entire target attribute into account may have a detrimental effect on the results.

More recent GAN-enabled frameworks fail to synthesize faces of extreme age ranges [32, 33]. Additionally, facial synthesis based on a single label (one hot vector) ignores the intra-class diversity of each age class and collapses it into a single ageing pattern. Consequently, conditioning face ageing synthesis on a single label ignores the intra-class diversity of each age class and results in images with a non-diverse ageing pattern. Therefore, GAN-based methods produce a single ageing per face biased by training data. Due to these deficiencies, such methods are ineffective for enhancing diversity in data since they tend to result in algorithmic bias when trained on biased synthetic datasets [8].

To address these issues, this study proposes the use of Selective Transfer Units (STUs) and skip connections between encoder and decoder layers, which inspired by the success of STGAN and taking a difference attribute vector as input and incorporating selective transfer units into an encoder-decoder structure [19]. STUs perform adaptive selections and modifications of the encoder features. These features are then

concatenated with decoder features to enhance the quality and capture local and global ageing-related attributes. The skip connections between the encoder and decoder layers typically result in training stability. In recent studies, multi-level facial features extracted from images were found to contain more texture and style features if multiple scales of discriminators were employed and can force the generator to synthesize by adversarial loss to produce vivid ageing effects [33, 14]. As shown in Fig 1 (a) a manifold learning-based model, feature translation, and StyleAging do not preserve identity in the presence of hair, mustache, or beard effects in the 50+ age group. Our MuSTAT model captures a more ageing pattern while preserving identity.

The contributions of this work are as follows:

- (i) A proposed Multi-Scale Target Age Style Transfer (MuSTAT) approach that is novel to transfer face age model and can generate more realistic results than prior models.
- (ii) A selective transfer unit is incorporated at the initial layers of the encoder-decoder to capture local and global face ageing patterns simultaneously. Furthermore, the proposed approach uses skip connection to provide training stability as an inherent advantage. MuSTAT can generate faces with large intra-class diversity while preserving the identity by focusing on the target image instead of a target class.
- (iii) Our model can retain identity information while preserving gender, hairstyle and background. The experiments on FRS indicate 89.82% False Non Match Rate (FNMR) at False Match Rate (FMR) of 0.0001% using Elastic-Cos+ [2] while we obtain a $FNMR = 100\%$ at $FMR = 0.01\%$ using Probabilistic Face Embedding (PFE) [30].
- (iv) The experiment results indicate that the proposed approach can capture face ageing. While existing models can create ageing images up to 50 years, our model is able to capture ageing beyond 60 years.

2 Related Works

2.1 Encoder-Decoder Architecture

Hinton et al. [11] proposed an autoencoder network consisting of an encoder and decoder to map the input into a latent vector and a decoder to recover from the latent vector. Subsequently, denoising autoencoders were proposed to learn representations robust to partial corruption. Kingma et al.[16] suggested a Variational autoencoder (VAE) which validates the feasibility of encoder architecture to generate unseen images. Recent studies [26] between encoder and decoder layers usually provide training stability and visual quality. StarGAN [6] adopted an encoder-decoder structure, where spatial pooling or downsampling are essential to obtain a high-level abstract representation for attribute manipulation. Unfortunately, downsampling irreversibly diminishes spatial resolution and fine details of feature maps due to transposed convolution which results in blurry or missing information. STGAN [19] developed selective transfer units (STU) to adaptively transform encoder features guided by attributes to be changed and enhance the image quality of editing.

2.2 Generative Adversarial Networks

Goodfellow et al. [9] proposed Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) for various applications, including image generation, image super-resolution, text-to-image syn-

thesis, and image-to-image translation, following the min-max rule to train the network. Several works were presented to improve GAN image quality and stability. First, Radford et al. [24] introduced the deep convolutional generative adversarial network architecture (DCGAN). To overcome the vanishing gradient, mode collapse and improve network stability, methods like LSGAN [28] and WGAN [1] are proposed. The conditional generative adversarial network (cGAN) [21] is a variant of GAN, which uses a class label as a condition to synthesize a target image. Face ageing can be considered a sub-problem of image-to-image translation, which involves converting an input image from one domain to another while preserving its original identity. Isola et al. [13] introduced pix2pix, which requires paired datasets to learn picture-to-picture translations. On the one hand, it is impractical to collect paired images with and without desirable attributes (e.g., female and male face images of the same person in different age). CycleGANs [37] have recently been successfully used for image-to-image translation tasks, overcoming the need for a paired dataset and achieving reliable results. In the most recent trend of style transfer work, style content is modulated explicitly at different layers with Adaptive Instance Normalization [7].

2.3 Style Transfer

Style transfer is a computer vision approach that allows us to impose the style of one image on the other image content. It takes two images as input content and style images and merges them so that the resulting output image keeps the essential components of the content image. However, the results tend to appear as “painted” in the style of the reference image. Gatys et al. [7] introduced the first neural style transfer algorithm by integrating feature statistics in convolutional layers of a DNN which resulted in impressive style transfer. However, given a slow optimization process, subsequent works were proposed to improve style transfer speed and quality. Li et al. [18] demonstrated that several other statistics are similarly beneficial for style transfers, including the channel-wise mean and variance. Huang et al. [12] proposed a method to resolve the slow optimization process and presented an adaptive instance normalization concept that aligns the mean and variance of content and style attributes.

2.4 Face Ageing

Traditional methods such as physical model-based and prototype-based models are computationally expensive and require large paired datasets at varying ages [10]. Recently, deep learning-based approaches using GANs and its variant Conditional GANs (cGANs) [21] have made a breakthrough in generating high-quality images and image translation. Several studies for facial ageing based on GANs [33] and cGANs [36, 32, 4] have been proposed, using unpaired datasets and generating good results. These methods learn the ageing patterns between two groups and map functions to translate faces, given target age as a condition. However, the generated results often show ghosting artifacts due to the increasing age gap (See Fig 1(a)). Due to the intrinsic complexities (like gender, race, and expressions) of face ageing, these approaches do not guarantee smooth ageing results. Further, they do not preserve age-invariant attributes and suffer

from identity loss. To preserve identity, recent works have introduced identity consistency [32, 36, 33].

3 Proposed Network Architecture

To tackle the limitations listed in related works, we used a style-based face ageing model, where instead of passing just age as a condition, a style image of the target age is used along with the source image. We further introduce a selective transfer unit block to transfer selective attributes from encoder to decoder. Instead of passing just age as a condition, we pass a style image of the target age along with the source image. In addition to protecting identity information, we focus on improving the diversity of intra-class ageing patterns based on distinct intrinsic and extrinsic factors using a multi-scale age discriminator.

Our proposed MuSTAT model comprises two components, i.e., a style generator (G) and multi-scale age discriminator (D). Figure 2 illustrates the network architecture of G consisting of encoder G_{enc} for latent abstract representation and a decoder G_{dec} for target image generation with ageing effect. (D) is incorporated to synthesize an image of desired target age, given a source image of a particular age and a style image of desired target age. The source face image $x_s \in \mathbb{R}^{h \times w \times 3}$, of age s along with a style image $\hat{x}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{h \times w \times 3}$ of desired target age t ; is passed through the generator and discriminator (where h and w are the height and width of image), to obtain a target image \tilde{x}_t with ageing effects of target class.

Fig. 2: The architecture of proposed MuSTAT model. The block on the top right corner shows the STU used in the proposed architecture.

3.1 Style Generator

The generator, as shown in Fig 2 follows an auto-encoder architecture, with an encoder G_{enc} and decoder G_{dec} . The encoder G_{enc} takes input a source image x_s and generates a feature map z ; $z = G_{enc}(x_s)$. The encoder having E^l as intermediate layer, can be formulated as $G_{enc} = E^N \circ E^{N-1} \circ \dots \circ E^1$, where the symbol \circ denotes function composition. The output for layers $l \in \{1, N\}$ is $f^l = E^l(f^{l-1})$; where $f^0 = x_s$ and

so, $z = f^N$. Similarly, the decoder having D^l as intermediate layer, can be formulated as $G_{dec} = D^N \circ D^{N-1} \circ \dots \circ D^1$ and, the multi-scale age discriminator (D_{msa}) having C^l as intermediate layer, can be formulated as $D_{msa} = C^{N+1} \circ C^N \circ C^{N-1} \circ \dots \circ C^1$. The discriminator output for layers $l \in \{1, N\}$ is $g^l = C^l(g^{l-1})$; where $g^0 = \hat{x}_t$. The target age style is extracted from \hat{x}_t by all layers of multi-scale age discriminator (D_{msa}). The age style is then injected into the decoder of the style generator (G) using adaptive instance normalization (AdaIN) [12].

Selective Transfer Unit (STU) We introduced the Selective Transfer Unit (STU) block in the skip connections to capture local and global face ageing patterns simultaneously. At the first three layers of this skip connection, we added the STU blocks [19], which selectively transform the encoder feature and pass it to the decoder. Thus, for layer $l \in \{1, 3\}$ -

$$h^l = AdaIN(D^l(h^{l-1} + STU(f^{N-l+1}, s^{N-l+2})), g^{N-l+1}); \quad (1)$$

where $h^0 = z$ and $s^4 = f^4$

And for any layer $l \in \{1, N\}$,

$$h^l = AdaIN(D^l(h^{l-1} + f^{N-l+1}), g^{N-l+1}) \quad (2)$$

Fig 2 shows the architecture of the GRU-based STU unit. For l^{th} layer, where f^l is the feature output from l^{th} layer of encoder and s^{l+1} is the hidden state from $l + 1^{th}$ layer. $r^l = \sigma(W_r * [f^l, s^{l+1}])$, $z^l = \sigma(W_z * [f^l, s^{l+1}])$, $s^l = r^l \otimes s^{l+1}$, $\hat{f}_t^l = \tanh(W_h * [f^l, s^l])$

$$STU(f^l, s^{l+1}) = (1 - z^l) \otimes s^{l+1} \oplus z^l \otimes \hat{f}_t^l \quad (3)$$

here, $*$ is convolution operation; \otimes is element wise product; \oplus is element wise sum; $[\cdot, \cdot]$ is concatenation operation; $\sigma(\cdot)$ sigmoid function. Adding the reset gate (r^l) and update gate (z^l) allows us to manage the contribution of hidden state (s^{l+1}) and encoder features (f^l) selectively.

U-Net Skip connection:

To recover spatial information lost during down-sampling, Ronneberger et al.[26] proposed U-Net skip connections in the encoder-decoder architecture. Output from each layer of encoder is element-wise added to each corresponding layer of decoder. The decoder takes the feature map z as input along the skip connections and adds up style information passed from discriminator using the Adaptive Instance Normalization (AdaIN) [12] layer to give a synthesized image \hat{x}_t as output. So the output of decoder for any layer $l \in \{1, N\}$: $h^l = AdaIN(D^l(h^{l-1} + f^{N-l+1}), g^{N-l+1})$

3.2 Multi-scale Age Discriminator

A discriminator detects whether an image belongs to a real or fake image. As the images are classified into four age groups, we used a few-shot unsupervised multi-task

discriminator [20]. To detect whether an image is a real one belonging to class s_i or a generated one. The discriminator output is $y = C^{N+1}(g^N)$, where y yields the score for the s_i class to which it corresponds or is the target class. The resulting network captures features representing both the “realness” of the faces and their age. (D_{msa}) is mirrored G_{dec} of G to maintain correspondence between features at different scales.

4 Loss Function

The aim is to optimize the MuSTAT to achieve four main goals of ageing: (i) Better quality of the synthesized image, (ii) Diversity in the ageing pattern, (iii) Enforcing cycle consistency, and (iv) Preserving the identity of the original image. Therefore, we used four respective types of loss functions for training:

Adversarial loss: To achieve a better quality of synthesized image, we train the network with the min-max loss. The generator tries to minimize the loss given in Eqn (4) while the discriminator tries to maximize it. Given an input face image x_s of source age s and a style image \hat{x}_t of target age t , to generate \tilde{x}_t the synthesized image from $\tilde{x}_t = G(x_s, \hat{x}_t)$, the adversarial loss is calculated as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{adv} = \mathbb{E}_{x_s} [\log(D_{msa}(x_s))] + \mathbb{E}_{x_s, \hat{x}_t} [\log(1 - D_{msa}(\tilde{x}_t))] \quad (4)$$

Feature Matching loss: The model would not converge and cause a mode collapse problem due to the greedy nature of optimization in the min-max game between generator and discriminator. During the training of the multiscale age model, it is important to identify the features that discriminate between real data and synthesized data in MuSTAT model. We therefore use feature loss [28] that modifies the generator’s cost function to minimize the statistical difference between real and synthesized image features. As a result, feature matching broadens the aim beyond defeating the opponent to matching features in real-world images. We train the generator to match the expected value of the features on an intermediate layer of the discriminator. The loss is calculated between input style image \hat{x}_t and the synthesized image \tilde{x}_t . The feature loss is -

$$\mathcal{L}_{fm} = \mathbb{E}_{\hat{x}_t} \|g(\hat{x}_t) - g(\tilde{x}_t)\|_2^2 \quad (5)$$

$g(x)$ is the feature vector extracted from an intermediate layer of the multi-scale age discriminator D_{msa} .

Cycle Consistency loss: Cycle GAN [37] uses the forward cycle consistency loss to learn mapping and $M : x_s \rightarrow \tilde{x}_t$ and $N : \tilde{x}_t \rightarrow x_s$. We want to enforce the intuition that these mappings should be preserved between x_s and x_t . This loss ensures that $N(M(x_s)) \approx x_s$ and $M(N(\tilde{x}_t)) \approx \tilde{x}_t$.

$$\mathcal{L}_{cc} = \mathbb{E}_{x_s, \tilde{x}_t} \|x_s - G(x_s, \tilde{x}_t)\|_1 \quad (6)$$

Identity Loss: The adversarial loss makes the generator generate faces from the target distribution. The resulting face can resemble any person in the target age group. The identity of the synthesized image therefore must be preserved for face recognition applications. Along with the adversarial loss we added the identity loss, calculated between the original face image and the synthesized image.

$$\mathcal{L}_{id} = \mathbb{E}_{x_s, \tilde{x}_t} [\|x_s - \tilde{x}_t\|_1] \quad (7)$$

Regularization: The R1 regularization technique is used to stabilize the discriminator. The discriminator is penalized for diverging from the Nash Equilibrium solely based on real data. The gradient penalty assures that the discriminator cannot construct a non-zero gradient orthogonal to the data manifold without losing the GAN min-max game when the generator distribution yields the genuine data distribution and the discriminator is equal to 0 on the data manifold. They apply the following regularization term on the synthesized image \tilde{x}_t and add to the discriminator loss.

$$\mathcal{L}_{gp} = \lambda_{gp} \mathbb{E}_x \|\nabla D_{msa}(\tilde{x}_t)\|_1 \quad (8)$$

Objective Function: To train the generator G they use the feature matching loss (5), cycle consistency loss (6) and the identity loss (7). The generator loss \mathcal{L}_G is:

$$\mathcal{L}_G = \mathcal{L}_{fm} + \lambda_{cc} \mathcal{L}_{cc} + \lambda_{id} \mathcal{L}_{id} \quad (9)$$

And, train the discriminator with adversarial loss (4), and add a regularization term (8) to stabilize the discriminator using $\mathcal{L}_{D_{msa}}$ loss. Where, $\lambda_{cc} = 0.01$, $\lambda_{id} = 10^{-4}$, $\lambda_{gp} = 10.0$.

$$\mathcal{L}_{D_{msa}} = \mathcal{L}_{adv} + \mathcal{L}_{gp} \quad (10)$$

5 Experiments and Results

Fig. 3: Ageing results generated by IPCGAN, CPAVAE, Georgopoulos et al.[8] and our MuSTAT on two images from CACD dataset (Zoom for better view).

5.1 Dataset

Cross-Age Celebrity Dataset: CACD [5] dataset is the largest publicly available cross-age face dataset, consisting of over 160,000 images of 2,000 celebrities aged 16 to 62 [5]. We used 90% of the dataset for training and 10% for testing purposes. The dataset has significant variations in pose, illumination, and even style. For data pre-processing, we used MTCNN [34] to detect the five landmarks points (two eyes, nose, and two mouth corners) used for proper alignment and to crop the images to a resolution of 128×128 pixels before passing images into MuSTAT model. For our experiments, the dataset was divided into four age groups such as $G1(0-30)$, $G2(31-40)$, $G3(41-50)$, and $G4(50+)$, respectively. **FGNET:** To inspect the robustness of our proposed MuSTAT approach, we also adopt FGNET [17] for the testing phase only. FG-NET contains 1,002 face images from 82 subjects, with age ranging from 0 to 69 and an age gap up to 45 years.

5.2 Implementation Details

To evaluate the proposed model, we compare MuSTAT with IPCGAN [32], CPAVAE [22], CAAE [36] and Georgopoulos et al [8] on two datasets explained before. Our proposed model is trained using Adam optimizer ($\beta_1 = 0.5, \beta_2 = 0.0.999$) with a learning rate 0.0001 and hyperparameters with $\lambda_{cc} = 0.01, \lambda_{id} = 10^{-4}, \lambda_{gp} = 10.0$.

6 Qualitative evaluation

6.1 Experiment I: CACD Dataset

Fig 3 presents sample results on face ageing using three state-of-the-art models for a male and a female subject. It can be noted from the figures that the manifold learning-based CPAVAE model beautifies images and does not preserve skin color. It removes wrinkles when synthesizing old faces from young face source input due to pre-trained VGG19 perceptual loss. CPAVAE generates relatively smooth images with less age progression effects. IPCGAN based on feature translation approach alters the face region alone to preserve the identity but cannot generate better-ageing effects such as wrinkles, hair and variation in skin texture. While Georgopoulos et al.[8] can generate both young and old-aged faces with ageing effects, artifacts appear near the eyes and produce unrealistic the moustache and beard concerning age group (Ref Fig 3). However, the proposed MuSTAT model can produce results of higher visual fidelity, especially if the last age group (G_4) is considered. A similar trend can also be noticed for a female subject as shown in Fig 3. Compared to the Georgopoulos et al.[8] model, our proposed approach results in high-fidelity images by preserving the identity occluded forehead. While IPCGAN and CPAVAE produce unrealistic colors hair colors, our approach can preserve realistic hair color. Further, looking at the results for G_1 category, one can note that our proposed approach can preserve gender identity compared to Georgopoulos et al.[8]. We take a detailed look at the results as shown in Fig 1 (a), where one can note the superiority of the proposed approach. Specifically, the proposed approach can handle nasolabial folds, facial skin changes, adjusted moustache and beard, and detailed wrinkles.

7 Quantitative Evaluation

Our experiments are benchmarked against three state-of-the-art face-ageing models [32, 22, 8] using the publicly available DEX [27] age estimator model. We further employ 6 different FRS models for establishing the results of Identity Preservation.

7.1 Ageing Variation

To measure the ageing variation of proposed approach, we first generate images corresponding to different age categories for each image. We measure the Mean-Absolute difference across different age groups to measure the variation from generated images computed from DEX age estimator model. Fig 4a and Fig 4b show the estimated ages calculated using the age estimator on the generated images for each age group. It shows

that IPCGAN and CPAVAE’s estimated ages on the generated images have overlapping distribution for all age groups and can mainly generate images between 20-40 age intervals. The proposed method can diversify its range and generate images in different age groups. Fig 4a shows that CPAVAE fails to produce aged and beyond 40 year age group when used for age-progression while the proposed MuSTAT is able to generate image in larger age groups (G3 and G4). Further, considering a age-regression scenario, one can also note that the proposed approach is able to generate younger age images from an older age group as shown in Fig 4b. The results indicate the ability of MuSTAT model to capture the central distribution density in terms of age categories.

Fig. 4: Distribution of estimated ages on generated images for (a) age progression (b) age regression with i) IPCGAN ii) CPAVAE iii) Georgopoulos et al.[8] and iv) MuSTAT.

7.2 Identity Preservation using Face Recognition

To evaluate the identity preservation of the proposed approach and compare it against state-of-the-art models, we employ six different FRS namely, FaceNet [29], PFE [30], and four variant of ElasticFace [2]. We specifically evaluate the FRS performance on CACD test datasets by creating impostor and genuine image pairs. Genuine pairs are formed using generated images of the largest age category (G4) against lowest age category (G1) for age progression and vice versa for regression. We present the results of FRS evaluation using FNMR at various FNMR as provided in Table 1. Our proposed MuSTAT model competes with IPCGAN and Georgopoulos et al.[8] when evaluated using different FRS on CACD. MuSTAT and Georgopoulos et al. achieve 100% verification rates at 0.1% FNMR using PFE and ElasticFace, respectively. The legacy models like CAAE and CPAVAE across all FRS have very low accuracy as they modify local and global face attributes. It is also evident that MuSTAT achieves far better accuracy than IPCGAN, CAAE and CPAVAE while competing equally with Georgopoulos et al. It can be seen from the results that the face verification accuracy is better when recent models like Elastic-Arc, Elastic-Cos, Elastic-Arc+, and Elastic-Cos+ are used as compared to relatively older FaceNet and PFE.

8 Conclusion and Future work

In this paper, we have proposed a multi-scale age-style transfer for face ageing. Our MuSTAT approach leverages selective transfer in a GAN framework. The proposed

Table 1: Face verification (%) of different face aging models using FRS on CACD.

Ageing	FaceNet			PFE			Elastic-Arc			Elastic-Cos			Elastic-Arc+			Elastic-Cos+		
	FNMR@FMR	$1e-2$	$1e-3$	FNMR@FMR	$1e-2$	$1e-3$	FNMR@FMR	$1e-2$	$1e-3$	FNMR@FMR	$1e-2$	$1e-3$	FNMR@FMR	$1e-2$	$1e-3$	FNMR@FMR	$1e-2$	$1e-3$
IPCGAN	99.89	99.26	78.87	99.93	99.26	99.67	77.96	98.80	99.93	99.91	99.67	90.65	99.93	98.80	75.85	9.95	99.65	90.04
CPAVE	34.27	13.03	2.84	30.12	12.23	2.88	29.33	10.30	3.51	33.64	13.18	3.66	30.60	11.47	3.62	34.81	13.70	4.68
CAAE	52.66	29.28	10.95	53.08	30.91	17.28	49.28	25.92	13.16	55.57	32.77	16.48	51.06	26.96	12.29	56.05	32.47	14.81
Georgopoulos	99.84	98.35	81.93	99.97	98.85	99.97	100.0	98.59	89.80	100.0	99.21	94.33	100.0	98.52	88.24	100.0	99.32	94.14
MuSTAT	99.80	97.20	88.55	100.0	96.68	85.40	99.97	94.96	86.50	99.97	94.96	86.50	99.97	96.65	89.26	99.97	97.09	89.82

model can achieve progressive and regressive ageing effects with a high-fidelity visual appearance. Further, the model can transfer selective effects related to ageing to the real image using the style images. Experimental results on public datasets demonstrate that MuSTAT can produce ageing details in a superior manner compared to existing state-of-the-art works. We verify the diversity of face age generated using the proposed approach by employing DEX age estimator. In addition, we also evaluate the general application for face recognition using six different FRS to establish the identity preservation ability of the proposed approach. Future works in this direction should consider extending this idea to 3D facial age modeling and simulation for cross-age face recognition.

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